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Where is the nest? A peculiar mode of synanthropic nesting of *Lasius niger* (L.) (Hymenoptera: Formicidae)

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Abstract: *Lasius niger* (L.) is a common ant species with strong synanthropic tendencies. It commonly occurs in various anthropogenic environments, including the immediate vicinity of human habitations. In Europe, *L. niger* is one of the most numerous species in urban habitats; its gynes, fertilised during their nuptial flights, sometimes fall onto balconies in residential buildings, where they are able to give rise to new colonies. Described and discussed here is the functioning of such a *L. niger* colony and its unusual way of nesting under the Styrofoam insulation of a concrete wall, i.e. in conditions very much unlike those in nests typical of the species.

Key words: adaptability, ants, extreme habitat conditions, flexibility of nesting, foraging, *Lasius niger*, synanthropy.

INTRODUCTION

How to get rid of ants on your balcony: the complete guide; Top tips and remedies to get rid of ants; 23 effective strategies for getting rid of ants on your balcony; Little black ants on balcony – should I be concerned?; My battle with ants: how to kill them for sure; Ants suddenly appearing on my balcony garden; Help, ants in balcony pots [...]; Is it a balcony for ants?; How to treat ants in balcony?; Do plants and flowers on an apartment balcony attract pests such as ants, [...] ? If so, how do you prevent it from happening? – these are the first-page responses from an online search engine when queried with the phrase ‘Ants on balcony’. This, as well as the tone of discussions on online forums, proves, on the one hand, how common ant phobia is among people and, on the other hand, how strong are the synanthropic tendencies in some ants. The species or genus of ants is rarely mentioned on these occasions, but the descriptions and photos show that in Europe, the culprits are the Black Garden Ants, i.e. *Lasius niger* (L.).

Lasius (*Lasius*) *niger* (LINNAEUS, 1758) is a Euro-Siberian species. Its range is difficult to determine based on current literature data due to taxonomic complexities. It certainly occurs in most of Europe, up to the Arctic Circle in the north; in Asia it reaches at least the Transbaikal region and Mongolia. It has been introduced to northern Africa (Algeria) and North America (Canada, USA, Mexico), where it occurs mainly in cities (SEIFERT 2018, SCHÄR *et al.* 2022, respectively). In Europe, it is one of the commonest ant species.

Ecologically, *L. niger* is a moderately hygro- and thermophilic polytope of open grassy habitats, also found in light forests; it avoids shaded woodlands and mires (CZECHOWSKI *et al.* 2012, RADCHENKO 2016, SEIFERT 2018). In ant assemblages, it plays the role of a pioneering succession species; it is the first to colonise newly created environments (e.g. freshly established urban lawns; W. CZECHOWSKI unpubl.), as well as early successional stages of natural environments (e.g. rocky islets; CZECHOWSKI *et al.* 2013). It is a typical ant species in various anthropogenic environments (agrocoenoses, pastures, as well as industrial, ruderal and urbanized areas); it usually prevails in the myrmecofaunas of European cities, e.g. Warsaw (PISARSKI & CZECHOWSKI 1978, CZECHOWSKI 1991, ŚLIPIŃSKI *et al.* 2012, TRIGOS-PERAL *et al.* 2020). It nests mostly in the soil, often under stones (in cities, under paving slabs and at curbs). In meadows with tall vegetation, it builds earthen mounds (up to several dozen centimetres high) above the underground part of the nest. Mature colonies are strictly monogynous, and number several thousand (sometimes tens of thousands) workers (CZECHOWSKI *et al.* 2012, RADCHENKO 2016, SEIFERT 2018). New colonies are established in a claustral manner by gynes fertilised during nuptial flight.

Lasius niger ants are omnivorous: predatory and scavenging on small invertebrates, trophobiotically associated with aphids and other producers of honeydew and sweet secretions; they also feed on nectar, sweet plant juices, etc. They can forage in all biocoenotic layers: in the soil, on the soil surface, in the herb layer and in tree canopies (CZECHOWSKI *et al.* 2012, RADCHENKO 2016, SEIFERT 2018). The species shows strong synanthropic tendencies; its foragers (from outdoor nests) often visit human habitations (houses and apartments on the ground floor) in search of food (sweets) and water. Nests on balconies of residential buildings (in pots and boxes with decorative plants) are established by foundatrices accidentally (or maybe not accidentally) landing there after nuptial flights (see CZECHOWSKI 2024).

This article describes the case of a special manner of nesting and the history of a mature *L. niger* colony on a balcony, which demonstrates the extraordinary ecological plasticity of these ants.

PLACE OF THE OBSERVATIONS; MATERIAL

The place of observations was a loggia-type balcony with a south-west exposure on the eight floor (ninth acc. to the US system) of an 11-storey large-panel residential block (inhabited in 1982) in the Ursynów district of Warsaw. The outer walls of the building, including the balcony walls, had originally been covered with white marble grit. In the 2010s, they were insulated with 10-centimeter-thick (point-mounted) facade foamed polystyrene (Styrofoam) boards and covered with a thin layer of plaster. Thus, a narrow vertical empty space filled with a maze of gaps between the stone chips was created between the Styrofoam layer and the solid wall, all along the surface of the entire building. This space, partly divided by balcony ceilings, is so spacious that mice can move there (gnawing out outputs in Styrofoam to the balconies, as in the case of the balcony in question).

The balcony on the floor above belonged to an apartment that had been practically abandoned for years. This balcony was probably completely empty, and certainly there were no live plants there. It served as a sleeping place for pigeons. The balcony below (the author's), on the contrary, was filled with numerous boxes and pots with decorative vegetation (Fig. 1).

The subject of the research was the colony of *L. niger*, which – already as a mature, quite large-sized one – moved from the balcony on the ninth floor to the author's balcony floor below, where it settled for good. The observations described here were made in the years 2022-2024, although *L. niger* ants had appeared on this balcony earlier.

Fig. 1. Vegetation on the balcony, which is a place of observation. Aphids on purslane (*Portulaca grandiflora*) in boxes on the balustrade in 2022 enticed *L. niger* ants from the balcony floor above (photo by W. Czechowski).

RESULTS

Within 42 years, the incipient colonies of *L. niger* repeatedly appeared in plant boxes on my balcony – not counting the colony consciously relocated by me with a flower pot from my previous apartment. All these colonies disappeared spontaneously after a shorter or longer time span.

In the spring of 2022, a dense two-way foraging trail of *L. niger* workers arrived on the insulated side wall of the balcony. The trail led from the balcony above [on the 9th floor (10th acc. to the US system)] not used for a long time (see Place and time of observations); it emerged from the very edge of the floor of that balcony, then led vertically down to my balcony (Fig. 2). Here the trail split: one part of the ants entered the upper edge of the balcony balustrade, the other part coursed to the lower edge, and along them spread to plant boxes of the upper row (suspended on the balustrade) and to the lower row (standing on the balcony floor), respectively. There the ants attended aphids on purslane (*Portulaca grandiflora*; Fig. 1), nasturtium (*Tropaeolum majus*), common morning-glory (*Ipomoea purpurea*), and others. This situation persisted until the end of the growing season 2022.

The next spring (2023) the foraging trail reappeared, initially along the previous routes, but its course changed during the season. As early as May, the ants no longer bypassed the edge of the floor/ceiling between the balconies on the 9th and 8th floor. The highest point of the trail visible from my balcony became a small gap on the junction of the balcony side wall

Fig. 2. The side wall of the balcony insulated with Styrofoam. The red arrow shows the original route of the *L. niger* trail between the balconies (in 2022 and at the beginning of the 2023 season); yellow dot – situation of the input/output of the trail under/from under the Styrofoam launched in May 2023; blue dot – the same launched in July 2023 (photo by W. Czechowski).

and ceiling (the junction of Styrofoam and concrete ceiling) (Fig. 2). Next, already invisible ants apparently used some crevices to get to the balcony floor above. Later, the visible part of the trail was shortened even more: in July, the exit of the foraging trail became a hole in Styrofoam (remnant of the hook), 1 m below the ceiling (Fig. 2 and 3). At the same time, an oblique branch of the trail was created, leading down to the aphids, which appeared on a potted ivy (*Hedera helix*) in the corner of the balcony where the ants could still be seen foraging (with weakening intensity) in November (Fig. 4); the ivy did not survive the winter. It is not known whether the rest of the former trail (i.e. upward of the outlet) ran under a layer of Styrofoam, and whether the change of the route was caused by a change of the nesting site of the colony or part of it. In late September, however, the ants stopped using this hole in Styrofoam and restored the former route of the trail to the ceiling. After a month (in late October), until the end of the season, they returned to exclusively using the hole in Styrofoam (Fig. 2).

Fig. 3. The *L. niger* trail to/from a hole in Styrofoam (blue dot in Fig. 2) (photo taken on 19 October, 2023 by W. Czechowski).

The intensity of traffic on the foraging trails was high, especially in the evening (and probably at night). On September 10-12 between 9 and 10 p.m. (at 23-25°C), the average number of workers traveling in one direction along the vertical section of the trail (toward the balustrade) in five minutes was 46.6 (± 12.3 ; $n = 30$).

In late October, the ants began to intensively penetrate the soil surface in the boxes placed on the balcony floor along the balustrade, and small groups of workers started to dig in the soil in the boxes. Next, the workers formed a trail to a large ivy pot in the corner of the balcony where they began to dig very intensively into the soil. At that time (and later), external activity of the ants was particularly high at night (Fig. 5) but ceased at a temperature below 8°C; then, at most individual ants were visible on the trails.

Starting from October 29, the ants began to be visible on the trails to newly formed soil auxiliary nests (in the ivy pot and boxes along the balustrade), carrying very small (1st stage) larvae. They were carried the larvae there and back – more or less equally often in both directions. It was not a mass phenomenon: a larva was carried by one in several dozen ants walking along the trail. This lasted at least until November 11. On November 8, the ants formed a new trail, directly connecting the nest in the ivy pot with ‘micronests’ in boxes

Fig. 4. A fragment of the *L. niger* foraging trail to aphids on an ivy (*Hedera helix*; in the lower right corner) (photo taken on 19 October, 2023 by W. Czechowski).

along the balustrade (bypassing the hole in Styrofoam). Larvae were also moved (in both directions) along this new trail. At the same time, there still was a trail from and to the hole in Styrofoam, which indicated that the (alleged) main nest of the colony remained somewhere under the Styrofoam.

The *L. niger* colony on the balcony maintained its activity, although at a very low level, practically throughout the entire (exceptionally warm) winter of 2023/2024. More or less regular trails operated at 8-10°C (Fig. 6), and individual ants were seen outside nests even at lower temperatures. Of course, the mobility of the ants under these conditions was significantly slower. I noticed the 'record holder' in this respect – alone and motionless on the trail route – on March 8, 2024 at 1.5°C (!); when the temperature rose to 4°C, it moved towards the ivy pot at a speed of 20 cm per five minutes. In other cases, for example, at 7°C (5-10 February), the speed of the ants on the exposed surface of the balcony wall was 3-10 cm per minute. The biological sense of this winter activity of the ants remains unknown (however, see Discussion); they moved in both directions along the previously established trails between the nests (i.e. the alleged main nest under the Styrofoam and auxiliary small soil nests in pots and boxes) without carrying anything. As it turned out, only a small part of the colony was involved in the winter activity. The rest (probably a large majority) wintered in nests. This was revealed when the ivy pot was raised accidentally: the tight space between the pot stand and the bottom of the pot (ca. 300 cm²) was filled with a layer of densely crowded semi-numb workers (without any offspring). After placing the pot in place, all the ants entered the pot through the hole in the bottom.

Fig. 5. Night activity of *L. niger* on the foraging trail (photo taken on 19 October, 2023 between 2 and 3 a.m. by W. Czechowski).

On February 10, when the temperature in full sunlight reached 29°C(!), the ants, after a long break, resumed the trail to (and from) the gap at the very top under the ceiling (see Fig. 2), while maintaining all previous trails. (Thus, the matter of location of the main nest has become even more mysterious). This trail was used (with breaks and at variable intensity; often alternately with the trail to/from the hole in Styrofoam a metre below; see Fig. 3) as long as until early April. In late April, the ants also launched intensive diffused penetration of the entire balcony, and drove a (micro) nest in the soil of the furthest flower box. They also became interested (temporarily) in gaps at the balcony doorstep, where they created a regular trail. There were also other new trails, including along the upper edge of the balustrade and on the floor along the entire row of boxes. At the turn of March and April, when warmer weather had become regular (day temperatures exceeding 20°C), the ants switched to mainly evening and night activity; single workers began to appear from 2-4 p.m., and continuous trails appeared after 8 p.m. Interestingly, 24-hour activity returned in the summer.

During March, I again noticed sporadic transport (in both directions) of very small larvae – this time between the soil nests in individual boxes along the balustrade and between these and the nest in the ivy pot. Later, at the turn of April and May, the larvae were transferred from boxes to the hole in Styrofoam. In mid-May, after 10 months of use of this hole, the

Fig. 6. Winter activity of *L. niger*; fragment of the trail to the Ivy pot with the wintering part of the colony (photo taken on 15 February, 2024 at around 10°C by W. Czechowski).

ants stopped using in one night, moving by a further 160 cm lower to the hole gnawed out in Styrofoam by mice, just below the fastening of the lower edge of the balustrade 10 cm above the floor (Fig. 7). The ants used this hole (sometimes sharing it with mice; see Discussion) – with a one-day break in late May, when they returned to using the hole above – until autumn. In mid-October the activity of ants almost expired, which gave the impression that they were preparing for wintering, or even that the colony was dying out. The situation changed radically at the end of the month. First of all, a change in the main nesting place of the colony that I had not noticed came to light then – the ants had moved from under the Styrofoam, as indicated by the ants' feeding practices.

Occasionally in 2023, and more systematically in 2024, I put out baits with a sugar or honey solution at various locations on the balcony, which the ants used eagerly (Figs 8 and 9), actively competing with (driving away) wasps (*Vespula vulgaris* L.). From July 2024, I started to feed the ants with carbohydrate food at a permanent location, namely, on a tray set on the table (incidentally, this prevented the ants spreading all over the balcony). Initially, a foraging trail to the bait formed, emerging from under the Styrofoam (from the 'mouse hole'); the trail was about 2.5 m long, and its last section coursed across the balcony wall which the table with the bait was placed next to. The intensity of using the trail (Fig. 10) left no doubt that it was made up of the ants from the main nest of the colony (then located somewhere under the Styrofoam).

On October 26, late in the afternoon – after a few colder days and a radical decrease in the ants' activity – there was a sudden reactivation of the trail to the bait on the table, but from

Fig. 7. Situation of the input/output of the *L. niger* trail under/from under the Styrofoam (orange dot) launched in May 2024), originally gnawed by mice; under the hole, Styrofoam particles are visible scattered on the floor by mice (photo taken by W. Czechowski).

another starting point. It was a soil nest which I had previously considered a small auxiliary nest in a pot with a jasmine tobacco (*Nicotiana glauca*) very close to a balcony wall covered with tiling, facing the wall covered with Styrofoam, and separated from it with a row of boxes (also mainly with tobacco plants) on the balcony floor along the balustrade. Thus, the trail was extended with a nearly 4-meter section running on the upper edges of the boxes. On its route, the trail was joined by workers from the ‘micronests’ in boxes; such small auxiliary nests were located in at least four of the six boxes. At the end of the row of boxes, along the trail, within five minutes, on average, $46.6 (\pm 7.4)$ foragers ($n = 5$) went towards the bait between 4-5 p.m. (at a temperature of approx. 20°C). Further, the trail led through three plant pots in contact with each other, the last of which was the former ivy pot where previously a significant part of the colony would winter (probably with no brood) – now it hosted a spindle (*Eunymus fortunei*). Past the pots, only single workers sporadically joined the trail from the recently (at least until early October) intensively used track from under the Styrofoam.

The increased activity of the ants probably persisted overnight, because from the very morning the following day (October 27) the trail was still being intensively used, but only some ants walking towards the bait reached it. Most stopped in the spindle pot, where they entered (and left) by means of a freshly dug burrow in the ground. Around 10 a.m., the ants began to massively take out the larvae of all stages(!) from the burrow and move them along the edge of the central (plantless) pot to the first pot with ivy seedlings and freshly scarified

Fig. 8. A bait for the ants (water sugar solution) on the balcony balustrade (photo taken on 29 August, 2023 by W. Czechowski).

Fig. 9. Bait for the ants (water honey solution) near the 'mouse hole' (photo taken on 19 May, 2024 by W. Czechowski).

soil – not less than 20 larvae per minute (Fig. 11). With unflagging intensity, this lasted to around 2 p.m., when the number of transferred larvae began to gradually decrease. So there must have been thousands of larvae there. On October 28 and 29, there was still considerable two-way traffic on the trail from the tobacco pot along the row of the boxes and through a set of three pots to the bait on the table. Some ants carried larvae (only 1st stage ones) – this time from the pot with ivy seedlings towards the tobacco pot (around noon it was a few larvae per minute) and, occasionally also back to the spindle pot. Starting from that day, until the end of the ants' activity in 2024, I no longer saw any ants using any entrance in the Styrofoam. In November, the trail was still operating when the temperature did not fall below 8°C, and the ants sporadically transferred small larvae in both directions between individual soil nests in the boxes and pots.

These events clearly point to a move of the balcony *L. niger* colony from under the Styrofoam, along with the offspring (and probably with the queen, if present), to the soil nest system in plant pots and boxes. This most likely happened at night (if suddenly) or nights (if gradually), because during the day it would practically not have passed unnoticed. In the following days, the larvae were distributed between individual nests, presumably according to needs and conditions. At the same time, the ants searched for more (or alternative) shelters. In late October, they intensified the (so far poor) dispersed penetration of the entire balcony surface; as a result, they found (behind the tobacco pot) a crevice just above the balcony floor, leading under the tiling on the wall separating my balcony from the neighbouring balcony. The ants must have found a convenient space for them there because they formed a trail to this place from boxes along the bottom edge of the balustrade. This trail functioned until the end of ants' activity in November 2024.

Finally, I provide two pieces of information supplementing the above account:

(1) In addition to the carbohydrate food, starting from spring 2024, I occasionally provided the ants with protein food: freshly killed insects, mainly flies, but also fragmented adult European June beetles [*Amphimallon solstitiale* (L.)], larvae of nut weevils (*Curculio nucum* L.), and others, served near the nest entrance. In addition, in May and June 2024, the ants used different half-alive insects accidentally dropped by common starlings (*Sturnus vulgaris* L.), who were feeding their chicks in a breeding box hung on a wall above the nest entrance (see Fig. 2). It is difficult to say how the ants had met their requirements for protein food under balcony conditions on their own; once I saw them hunting a silverfish (*Lepisma saccharina* L.).

(2) On June 25, 2024, the mass nuptial flight of *L. niger* was held at Ursynów. For the reactions of the balcony *L. niger* colony to foreign conspecific gynes, both spontaneously appearing on the balcony and experimentally introduced there, see CZECHOWSKI (2024). I have never noticed the presence of the balcony colony's own sexuals.

DISCUSSION

New colonies in *L. niger* are established haplomerically (by a single gyne mated during a nuptial flight on her own) or pleometrically (by a few temporarily associated gynes) (SEIFERT 2018). In the light of knowledge about the height and course of *L. niger* nuptial flights, there is no doubt that such is the origin of colonies appearing on balconies. This is most probably how the colony on the ninth floor of a residential building discussed in this paper was established; balconies at an altitude of 27-30 m (and even higher) are within the range of flights of *L. niger* sexuals (see CZECHOWSKI 2024). The questions are (1) where the

Fig. 10. A fragment of the *L. niger* trail to the bait on the table photo taken on 16 July, 2024 by W. Czechowski).

Fig. 11. The relocation of the main part of the *L. niger* colony with larvae from the spindle pot (invisible in the photo; to the right of the white pot) to the pot with ivy seedlings (to the left of the white pot) (photo taken on 27 October, 2024 at 11 a. m. by W. Czechowski).

gyne-foundatrix found a convenient place for a nest on the abandoned and empty balcony, in which she could successfully lead the colony, and (2) what the ants had been feeding on there before they began to forage on my balcony floor below.

Regarding the first question, nesting under the Styrofoam insulation seems to be the most likely, the more so that only a side wall was insulated on this balcony. Consequently, the junction of the smooth insulated wall and the gritty non-insulated one would abound in gaps, through which the gyne could freely make its way under a layer of Styrofoam. The possibility of the colony originally nesting under the insulation was confirmed by its subsequent history – after it moved to my balcony, where it most likely settled under the Styrofoam layer at (maybe not right away) the junction of the insulated wall and the balcony floor – judging by the location of the last nest entrance (low above the floor; Fig. 7). The case described is an excellent illustration of the synanthropic tendencies and abilities of *L. niger*, but also shows a wide range of ecological plasticity, including nesting plasticity, of this species – here not being able to use any nest material, and thus not being able to build any constructions of its own, the ants drilled tunnels and chambers in the nest substrate, being, therefore, practically unable to regulate climatic conditions in the nest (temperature, humidity, aeration). As a very potent pioneer species, *L. niger*, successfully colonise even extremely unfavourable habitats like bare rocky outcrops (CZECHOWSKI *et al.* 2013), quarries (COLLINGWOOD 1979) or post-mining slag heaps barely covered with vegetation (SEIFERT 2018, B. SYPIEŃ, unpubl.). However, even in such locations, it is rather unlikely for such harsh nesting conditions to occur as those on the balcony under the Styrofoam. Equally unfortunate (although due to the opposite thermal conditions in winter) could be the possible nesting of the colony under the tiling of another balcony wall – a place found and explored by the ants in autumn 2024.

The diet of the ants while they lived in their previous place remains a great unknown. In my opinion, at the time of moving onto my balcony, the colony had well over a thousand workers, which, according to A. Buschinger's data quoted by SEIFERT (2018), corresponds to a 2-3-year-old colony. Maybe it was some mesofauna associated with pigeon guano, feathers or dandruff. Cannibalism towards dead nestmates, as in the case of ants *Formica polyctena* FÖRST, trapped in an underground bunker (see RUTKOWSKI *et al.* 2019) could also have played a role. The third possibility is feeding on trophic eggs laid by the queen or workers (or both), i.e., unfertilised non-viable eggs that social insects use as food, mainly for larvae (see BRIAN 1983). Trophic eggs contain more protein than fertilised ones (MATTE & BILLEN 2021). In *L. niger* trophic eggs can be laid by young queens (when founding a colony; e.g. KIPYATKOV 1979, BARONI URBANI 1991, MATTE & BILLEN 2021), as well as by workers (KHILA & ABOUHEIF 2008). *Lasius niger* workers are also able to produce males, laying viable unfertilised eggs (CRAWLEY 1912, van der HAVE *et al.* 1988). Such eggs could also be eaten, as *L. niger* larvae can also devour viable eggs (BARONI URBANI 1991). The possibility of worker egg-laying in the colony in question is all the more likely as in the autumn (October-November) of 2023, a significant proportion (nearly half) of workers walking along the trails (in both directions!) had noticeably enlarged gasters. Unfortunately, the autopsy of such individuals with a focus on the functionality of their ovaries failed. In 2024, distended gasters were only seen in workers returning to the nest from food sources. The last possibility is cannibalism towards *L. niger*'s own offspring (larvae), such as was demonstrated in experimentally starved breeding of *Fomica sanguinea* Latr. kept with an excess of slave pupae of *F. fusca* L. (CZECHOWSKI 1991, 1996).

Whether the ants had obtained carbohydrate food before they discovered its resources on my balcony, and, if so, where from, is not known. It is rather unlikely that they had had access to live plants with aphids somewhere else before. In general, the issue of the availability of

carbohydrate food for ants (which is, above all, aphid honeydew) in an urban environment, considered just with regard to *L. niger*, is unclear. TRIGOS-PERAL's *et al.* (2024) findings (in Warsaw) suggest a lower availability of high-quality carbohydrates in urban areas compared to rural ones. On the other hand, according to the findings (in Berlin) and conjectures of GABER *et al.* (2024), *L. niger* in the city may rely more on aphid honeydew than on other food resources that are rarer and more unpredictable there – providing that such an indirect inference, based on the increased defence of mutualist aphids against their enemies by *L. niger* foragers in the city (see GABER *et al.* 2024) is right.

There are more open questions. For example, what was the purpose (apart from integration of the fragmented colony) of the densely frequented trails between the main nest and auxiliary nests in late autumn 2023. At that time, besides (very few) larvae, the ants did not carry anything in their mandibles, and the enlarged gasters were seen in individuals going in both directions. Could this have been a way to distribute trophic eggs?

In the winter of 2023/2024, the (more or less intense) ants' activity on the balcony was almost uninterrupted (except for short periods of larger temperature drops). It was the warmest winter in the history of measurements in Poland. The months of February and March were particularly warm, when the average monthly air temperatures were 5.7°C and 6.7°C, respectively (IMWM-NRI 2024). Regardless of the general warming of the climate, cities are known as peculiar 'heat islands', where the temperature can be significantly higher than in non-urban areas (e.g. ZHOU *et al.* 2017). Additionally, the balcony *L. niger* colony could have been stimulated to exhibit external winter activity by a relatively high temperature in the nest itself as it was located under a thick layer of the Styrofoam insulation – certainly much higher than in normal underground nests in winter – the more so as the wall containing the nest was not a face wall, but it separated the balcony from the neighbouring apartment. Maybe this was the cause of 'indecision' of the workers, carrying the larvae there and back at the same time – from an excessively(?) warm nest in the wall to excessively(?) cold provisional auxiliary soil nests in the pots and boxes. In KIPYATKOV's (1995) breeding experiment, *L. niger* workers moved larvae to the cooler parts of the artificial nest with a temperature gradient. A nest located in the space between the Styrofoam layer and the stone-concrete wall could not actually provide the colony with a gradient of such factors as temperature or humidity. Thus, the ants were not able to choose optimal conditions according to the offspring's differential needs.

By the way, it is puzzling why there were so few larvae at the beginning of winter 2023/2024 and there were only larvae of the 1st instar. In *L. niger*, larvae are the wintering stage of offspring (KIPYATKOV 1995, 1996). It cannot be ruled out that the above-mentioned special nesting conditions caused some disorders in the reproductive cycle of the colony. It is also possible that they intermittently caused increased brood mortality. *Lasius niger*, like any species, has a temperature range, optimal for the development of offspring and the growth of a colony. An increase in temperature within this range accelerates the development cycle and favours colony growth (see e.g. PORTER 1988, ABRIL *et al.* 2010, CHICK *et al.* 2019). However, an excessive increase in temperature above this range may have a harmful effect on the colony, causing increased mortality due to thermal stress (PENNICK *et al.* 2017); for analysis of these dependencies in *L. niger* in an urban environment (including Warsaw) see TRIGOS-PERAL *et al.* 2024). This could have been the case with the *L. niger* colony in question: the overall benefit of being in a moderately insulated urban environment could be offset (at least partially) by peculiar (unregulated) nesting conditions. In this context, it should be noted that before the next winter (2024/2025) the *L. niger* colony moved from under the Styrofoam to the earth nests when it contained a lot of larvae of all stages; the latter

could have been the result of more intensive feeding of the ants, especially with protein food. It is difficult to say what prompted the colony to move from under the Styrofoam at the end of the 2024 season. It coincided with the autumn invasion of mice (in October I caught on the balcony seven mice coming out from under the Styrofoam through the hole, also used by the ants). So it is possible that the reason for the movement of the ants was their disturbance in the nest by mice – especially if the nest was near the mouse shelter somewhere under the Styrofoam.

Lasius niger, and especially its urban populations (TRIGOS-PERAL *et al.* 2024), shows a tendency to increase activity at night. According to SEIFERT (2018), *L. niger* switches to night activity in summer, when it is too hot for it during the daytime. For the colony discussed here, increased activity in the evening and at night in relation to daily activity was recorded in autumn 2023 – both in September, when it was still warm (up to 25°C), and in late October, when it was quite cold (slightly above 8°C) – and then in early spring (March–April) of the next year, when temperatures exceeded 20°C, then in autumn, when it was cold again. So this was probably the case throughout the two entire growing seasons in the balcony *L. niger* colony which is a feature of the urban populations of the species – according to TRIGOS-PERAL's *et al.* (2024) findings.

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